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Miriam Giparakis

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Miriam Ciparakis,¹ Hedwig Knötig,¹ Hermann Detz,^{2,3} Maximilian Beiser,¹ Werner Schrenk,² Benedikt Schwarz,¹ Gottfried Strasser,^{1,2} and Aaron Maxwell Andrews^{1,a)}

AFFILIATIONS

¹Institute for Solid State Electronics, TU Wien, Gußhausstraße 25-25a, 1040 Vienna, Austria

²Center for Micro- and Nanostructures, TU Wien, Gußhausstraße 25-25a, 1040 Vienna, Austria

³Central European Institute of Technology, Brno University of Technology, Purkynova 123, 612 00 Brno, Czechia

^{a)} Author to whom correspondence should be addressed: aaron.andrews@tuwien.ac.at

ABSTRACT

Quantum cascade detectors (QCDs) are mid-infrared and far-infrared, low-noise, photovoltaic detectors utilizing intersubband transitions. This Letter presents an InAs/AlAs_{0.16}Sb_{0.84} based QCD lattice matched to an InAs substrate. This material system exhibits properties like a low effective electron mass of the well material of 0.023 m_0 , beneficial for higher optical absorption strength, and a high conduction band offset of 2.1 eV, allowing the design of QCDs in the mid-infrared and near-infrared region. The presented QCD has a peak spectral response at 2.7 μm (0.459 eV), the center of a CO₂ absorption band. To enable top side illumination, a grating was implemented. This additionally bypasses absorption by the narrow bandgap 0.345 eV (3.54 μm) InAs substrate material. The QCD has a peak responsivity at a room temperature of 5.63 mA/W and a peak specific detectivity of 1.14×10^8 Jones.

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Quantum cascade detectors (QCDs) are mid-infrared (MIR) and far-infrared, intersubband, unipolar, photovoltaic, detectors, which operate at room temperature. They are characterized by a low noise, fast working principle with scattering rates in the picoseconds, as well as a narrow spectral response, ≤ 0.08 eV.^{1–3} The absorption spectrum, which is dependent on the material system intrinsic properties, like the conduction band offset (CBO), can be tailored over a wide energy/wavelength range done by varying the well and barrier widths in the heterostructure.

QCDs are fundamentally different than other classes of photodetectors like interband detectors, including type-II and other superlattice detectors, where optical transitions occur between the valence and conduction band.⁴ Interband detectors excel in the wavelength range between the visible and MIR and offer high responsivity (above 100 mA/W^{5,6}) as well as broad band absorption, typically exceeding 2 eV. Reported devices in the literature often require cooling and an applied bias.⁴ Recent devices work at room temperature, near 0 V bias,⁶ and up to 5 μm .⁵ The advantage of QCDs lies in longer wavelength photodetection and applications where high-speed detection is required: Recently, a QCD with a 3-dB bandwidth of more than 20 GHz was reported,⁷ compared

to the 3-dB bandwidth of up to 7.04 GHz for a type-II superlattice detector.⁵

QCDs are the competing intersubband technology to the more established quantum well infrared photodetectors (QWIPs)⁸ that typically require cooling and employ bound-to-continuum state transitions, while QCDs employ bound-to-bound state transitions. QCDs were first reported in 2002 by Hofstetter *et al.*⁹ Since then, QCDs found applications in chemical sensing,¹⁰ image sensing,¹¹ free space optical communication,¹² and due to their high-speed detection⁷ QCDs can be used for the characterization of frequency combs.¹³ QCDs are most established in the MIR wavelength range,¹⁴ but they have also been demonstrated in the THz,¹⁵ around 2 THz (150 μm)¹⁶ and near infrared region.¹ Most QCDs are based on In_{0.53}Ga_{0.47}As/In_{0.52}Al_{0.48}As lattice-matched to InP substrates, which offer a CBO of 0.52 eV¹⁷ that can be extended in the strain-balanced case.¹⁸ To explore the short wavelength- to near-infrared region and increase the application wavelengths of QCDs, material systems with a higher CBO are required. The candidates are group III nitrides (the CBO of GaN/AlN is 1.7 eV)¹⁹ in which the shortest absorption wavelengths for QCDs were shown and barrier alloys with AlSb, for example In_{0.53}Ga_{0.47}As/AlAs_{0.56}Sb_{0.44} lattice matched to InP (CBO of 1.6 eV)²⁰

and InAs/AlAs_{0.16}Sb_{0.84} lattice matched to InAs substrates (CBO of 2.1 eV).²¹ These material systems are less developed because of the more challenging growth of mixed group V compounds, like As and Sb. The barriers and wells of QCDs designed for shorter wavelengths now become remarkably thinner, due to the high optical transition energy, which additionally complicates the growth. Another important parameter for QCDs is the effective electron mass m_e^* of the well material. A smaller m_e^* leads to an increased optical transition strength and, due to decreased scattering rates, leads to a higher resistance and lower noise, which improves the specific detectivity.²¹ Out of these three material systems, InAs has the lowest effective electron mass of $m_e^* = 0.023 m_0$, vs $m_e^* = 0.043 m_0$ for InGaAs, and $m_e^* = 0.2 m_0$ for GaN.¹⁷

In this Letter, an InAs/AlAs_{0.16}Sb_{0.84} QCD grown lattice-matched to an undoped InAs substrate was fabricated. This material system benefits from a low effective electron mass, while simultaneously having a high CBO. High optical transition energies additionally lead to an increased resistance and, therefore, lower Johnson noise, which also improves the detectivity. The QCD presented in this work detects at a wavelength of 2.7 μm (0.467 eV); this is in the center of a CO₂ absorption band. This energy lies above the InAs bandgap of 0.354 eV.

Figure 1(a) shows the band structure of the QCD. Shown are the probability densities. The conduction band is depicted in gray, and the valence band edge is depicted in blue. The optical transition takes place in the first well (marked by a red arrow), followed by the longitudinal-optical (LO) phonon extraction ladder.

Notice the narrow type-II band alignment of the material system between the valence band edge of the barrier material to the conduction band edge of the well material of approximately 0.14 eV. The narrow wells needed for an absorption wavelength of 2.7 μm lift the ground state of the optical transition and effectively increase the bandgap.

The QCD band structure was designed using an 8-band kp -method formalism. The electron transport includes scattering mechanisms, such as LO- and acoustic phonon scattering, interface roughness scattering, and alloy scattering. For high optical transition

energies, as is the case here, the absorption efficiency is reduced, while the extraction efficiency is increased, which is utilized in the design. A vertical design for the optical transition is implemented, followed by an LO-phonon scattering extractor. The ground state has an energy difference of more than 120 meV to the lowest extractor state in order to reduce back-filling and increase the electron lifetime in the ground level, and this benefits the absorption efficiency.

The QCD was grown by molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) in a Riber-C21 system on an undoped InAs (001) substrate. The active region was repeated for 30 periods and was sandwiched between highly Si-doped ($2.5 \times 10^{19} \text{cm}^{-3}$) InAs top (50 nm) and bottom (150 nm) contacts. Lattice-matched AlAsSb layers were achieved by initially growing bulk AlAs_{0.16}Sb_{0.84} layers on InAs substrates.²² Lattice-matched layers drastically decrease stress inside the material, reducing the probability of generating defects, and thicker structures can be grown. This is in contrast to GaSb substrates, which would be transparent for the absorption wavelength of the presented QCD and would therefore allow illumination through the substrate enabling more wave guiding options, but the InAs/AlAsSb heterostructure on GaSb would be needed to be grown strain-balanced because lattice-matched growth is impossible. This limits the choices of well and barrier width and, thus, reduces the degrees of freedom in the design of the active region and in the applications. The accuracy of the layer thicknesses and the growth quality were optimized by taking growth rate variations caused by shutter transients into account, as well as implementing special shutter sequences to improve the layer interfaces similarly to Refs. 23–25. The diffusion of dopant atoms into the barrier material was considered in the layer structure and counteracted by shifting the doping just to the middle of the doped well.²⁶

The material quality of the grown QCD was characterized by high-resolution x-ray diffraction (HR-XRD) with a Philips MRD-Pro and a Digital Instruments atomic force microscope (AFM). Sharp superlattice peaks in the (004) ω -2 θ scan [see Fig. 1(b)] indicate low interface roughness between the grown layers. This is reinforced by the AFM scan shown in Fig. 1(c) from which a root mean square (RMS) for the surface roughness of 0.228 nm was measured from a

FIG. 1. (a) Band diagram of the grown InAs/AlAs_{0.16}Sb_{0.84} QCD. The layer sequence in nm is as follows: **1.50**, 1.38, **2.00**, 1.43, **2.00**, 1.55, **2.00**, 1.65, **2.00**, 1.75, **2.00**, 1.85, **2.00**, **2.00**, 2.15, **2.00**, 2.30, **2.00**, 2.50, **2.00**, 2.70, **1.50**, and 3.85. The bold printed layers represent the AlAsSb barriers. The underlined well is doped $n = 1.09 \times 10^{12} \text{cm}^{-2}$. Red arrows mark the optical transition. (b) HR-XRD (004) ω -2 θ scan and (c) $3 \times 3 \mu\text{m}$ AFM scan of the InAs/AlAs_{0.16}Sb_{0.84} QCD. The $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ AFM scan shows an RMS of 0.228 nm.

$10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ AFM scan. This is not significantly rougher than a commercially available InAs substrate with an RMS of approximately 0.2 nm .

QCDs follow the intersubband transition selection rule. Only light polarized in the growth direction is detected by the active region.²⁷ A top diffraction grating, allowing surface-normal illumination, was simulated using COMSOL and implemented. This also eliminates substrate absorption by the narrow bandgap (0.354 eV) InAs substrate, which would absorb light with wavelengths below $3.5 \mu\text{m}$. (The QCD is designed at $2.7 \mu\text{m}$.) The simulations were swept over the grating period, the duty cycle, and the etch depth. From these results, a diffraction grating period of $0.97 \mu\text{m}$, a duty cycle of 0.5 , and an etch depth of $980 \mu\text{m}$ were selected. Figure 2(a) shows an optical microscope image of a fabricated $240 \times 240 \mu\text{m}$ mesa. Label 1 is the extended top contact ($10/300 \text{ nm Ti/Au}$) that also frames the mesa. Label 2 is the mesa, which was defined by dry etching using a Cl/Ar process with an inductively coupled- and high frequency plasma process, into which the grating is etched over an $200 \times 200 \mu\text{m}$ area on the mesa about $1 \mu\text{m}$ deep using the same dry etching process, through the 50 nm thick InAs top contact and directly into the active region through approximately 20 periods, leaving 10 periods untouched. The dry etching process resulted in smooth, slightly positively sloped sidewalls (see inset of a focused ion beam cut through the grating). The mesa is surrounded on three sides by the bottom contact ($10/300 \text{ nm Ti/Au}$), which is label 3. The top and bottom contacts are separated and isolated by a 240 nm thick Si_3N_4 passivation layer. A sketch of the transverse device scheme is included as an inset in Fig. 2(b).

Optical measurements of the QCD were performed using a Bruker Vertex 70v Fourier-transform infrared spectrometer. A Globar was used as the broadband light source. Additionally, an Edmund Optics longpass filter with a specified cutoff wavelength of $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ (4000 cm^{-1} , $2.4 \mu\text{m}$ cut-on wavelength) was utilized to block nearby

interband absorptions. The QCD was top-side illuminated through the diffraction grating. In Fig. 2(b), the peak responsivity at different temperatures is shown. At room temperature, the average QCD responsivity at $2.73 \mu\text{m}$ (3650 cm^{-1}) of five characterized devices is 5.51 mA/W , ranging from 5.32 to 5.63 mA/W . While from about 200 to 80 K , a blue shift in the spectra occurs that is typically observed for QCDs;²⁸ there is negligible temperature dependence of the responsivity with a maximum of 7.49 mA/W . The temperature dependent responsivity measured inside the cryostat was scaled according to the responsivity measurement performed in ambient conditions in order to compensate for the reduced transmission of the cryostat ZnSe window and the shadowing of the beam by the window itself.

We achieved a higher responsivity and detectivity than the previous InAs/AlAs_{0.16}Sb_{0.84} QCD in the multipass 45 geometry with a room temperature responsivity of 1.9 mA/W at $4.84 \mu\text{m}$.²¹ It is important to note that the theoretical maximum of the responsivity scales directly proportional with the detection wavelength. The responsivity is also higher than for similar wavelength III-V QCDs, such as the In_{0.53}Ga_{0.47}As/AlAs_{0.56}Sb_{0.44} QCD from Giorgetta *et al.*²⁰ with a room temperature responsivity of 2.57 mA/W at $2.46 \mu\text{m}$ fabricated in the multipass 45 geometry.

From the peak responsivity, the specific Johnson noise limited detectivity can be calculated from

$$D = R_p \sqrt{\frac{R_0 A}{4k_B T}}, \quad (1)$$

where R_p is the responsivity, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature, and $R_0 A$ is the product of the differential resistance at zero bias and the optical area of the device, which is plotted in Fig. 2(c) with the calculated specific detectivity at different temperatures. At room temperature, a specific detectivity of 1.14×10^8 Jones was

FIG. 2. (a) Picture of a $240 \times 240 \mu\text{m}$ mesa. The extended top contact (1) frames the mesa and is $20 \mu\text{m}$ wide (2). The bottom contact (3) surrounds the mesa on 3 sides. The grating (see inset of a focused ion beam cut through the grating) is etched over a $200 \times 200 \mu\text{m}$ area of the mesa directly into the active region and through the top InAs contact of the QCD about $1 \mu\text{m}$ in total depth, leaving out only a $20 \mu\text{m}$ wide frame, where the gold contact was deposited. (b) Temperature dependent measured responsivity of the InAs/AlAs_{0.16}Sb_{0.84} QCD. A longpass filter with a specified cutoff wavelength of $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ ($2.4 \mu\text{m}$ cut-on wavelength) was used to block the nearby interband absorption. The inset depicts a sketch of the transverse device scheme: The black layers above the substrate and above the active region (AR) are the doped contact layers. The cyan layer is the Si_3N_4 passivation and the yellow layers the top and bottom Ti/Au contacts. The red arrows indicate the illumination direction. (c) Temperature dependent specific detectivity (to the left) and the $R_0 A$ product (to the right) are plotted. The fitted/calculated activation energy is 265 meV .

calculated. From the R_0A product plotted vs the temperature, an activation energy of 265 meV can be fitted.

In conclusion, an InAs/AlAs_{0.16}Sb_{0.84} QCD lattice matched to InAs is reported. Due to its high CBO, this one material system can cover a broad wavelength range from short- to far-infrared.^{21,29,30} HR-XRD and AFM indicate low interface roughness with an RMS measured from a $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ scan of 0.228 nm. The QCD has a room temperature peak responsivity of 5.63 mA/W at 2.7 μm (0.459 eV), and this energy lies above the bandgap energy of InAs, which is (0.354 eV) and in the center of a CO₂ absorption band. Such a device was realized by the utilization of a diffraction grating for top illumination. The detectivity at room temperature was calculated to be 1.14×10^8 Jones, and an activation energy of 265 meV was fitted/calculated.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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